

1 Low-Temperature Discharging Performance Comparison
2 of Sodium-Ion and Lithium-Ion Cylindrical Batteries

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9 **Abstract** This work presents a systematic comparison of the low-
10 temperature discharge performance of cylindrical sodium-ion (SIB) and
11 lithium-ion (LIB) batteries in the 18650 format. Two commercial SIB cells,
12 designed for high-energy and high-power applications, were evaluated
13 alongside three LIB chemistries: nickel–manganese–cobalt oxide (NMC),
14 lithium iron phosphate (LFP), and lithium titanate (LTO). Constant-current
15 discharge tests were conducted at temperatures from 25 °C to –40 °C to
16 assess capacity, energy, power, and thermal behavior. At room temperature,
17 NMC-based LIBs exhibited the highest energy density, but their usability
18 ends below –20 °C. LFP and LTO cells retained at least partial functionality
19 at –30 °C but failed at lower temperatures. This behavior is also similar for
20 SIB high-energy cells, whereas the high-power variant maintained stable
21 discharge across all tested rates to –30 °C and retained usable capacity even
22 at –40 °C. These results demonstrate that although SIBs possess lower
23 energy density than LIBs at ambient conditions, their superior resilience to

1 extreme cold makes them promising candidates for applications requiring
2 reliable operation in sub-zero environments.

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5 **Keywords** Batteries • Lithium-ion • Sodium-ion • Charge transfer •

6 Electrochemistry • Kinetics

7 (Four to six keywords, at least three should be taken from the keyword listing available at the Springer web
8 page: <http://www.springer.com/chemistry/journal/706> → Instructions for authors → Keyword list for
9 authors). The keywords should characterize the scope of the paper, the principal materials, and main
10 subjects. Do not duplicate words already contained in the title!

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17

1 **Introduction**

2 Reliable battery performance in low-temperature environments is critical for
3 various applications, such as space missions, outdoor systems, and
4 operations in cold climates [1]. Nevertheless, at low temperatures, lithium-
5 ion batteries (LIBs) exhibit significant performance limitations, typically
6 manifested as large overpotentials and severely reduced capacity due to
7 hindered Li^+ transport within the cell. Furthermore, electrolyte freezing is
8 expected below $-30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for commonly used LiPF_6 in ethylene
9 carbonate/ethyl methyl carbonate solvents [2]. Efforts to improve the low-
10 temperature performance of LIBs focus primarily on electrolyte and
11 electrode engineering, targeting issues like ion desolvation and charge-
12 transfer resistance at the electrode–electrolyte interface. Strategies include
13 using low-freezing-point solvent mixtures, EC-free electrolytes, and
14 engineered solid-electrolyte interphases (SEI) to enhance Li^+ mobility [1].

15 Another approach to achieving efficient low-temperature performance
16 in energy storage systems is to adopt an alternative technology that exhibits
17 more favorable behavior under such conditions. One promising candidate is
18 the recently commercialized sodium-ion battery (SIB). SIBs offer the
19 potential for lower cost and reduced dependence on critical materials, as they
20 use the more abundant sodium and can employ aluminum instead of copper
21 as the anode current collector [3]. Additionally, some manufacturers report

1 lower operational temperature limits compared to those typical for LIBs.
2 This improved behavior may be explained by the fact that, although SIBs
3 suffer from sluggish Na^+ diffusion at low temperatures, Na^+ ions can
4 desolvate more easily than Li^+ ions, potentially enabling faster interfacial
5 reactions, such as charging and discharging, under cold conditions [4].

6 Recent research has increasingly focused on evaluating the
7 performance of commercial SIBs in order to establish benchmarks
8 comparable to those available for LIBs. Dorau et al. conducted a
9 comprehensive structural and electrochemical analysis of four commercial
10 SIBs, revealing considerable variation in electrode coatings, particle sizes,
11 and cathode materials, and highlighting the critical role of these design
12 factors for performance and degradation, particularly at low temperatures
13 down to 0 °C [5]. Similarly, Marangon et al. systematically investigated
14 18650-type SIB cells with layered oxide cathodes and hard carbon (HC)
15 anodes, concluding that while sluggish Na^+ kinetics at the anode remain a
16 bottleneck, the overall cell performance is already getting close to certain
17 types of lithium iron phosphate (LFP)-based LIBs [6]. Rehm et al. directly
18 compared commercial SIBs with layered oxide cathodes to state-of-the-art
19 LFP cells within a 10-45 °C window, showing that although SIBs exhibit a
20 stronger dependence of impedance and efficiency on temperature and state
21 of charge, their C-rate capability is on par with the investigated LFP cells [7].

1 Thus, case-by-case comparisons have shown that SIB cells can approach, or
2 in certain metrics even surpass, LFP-based LIB cells in terms of specific
3 performance indicators. Nevertheless, their behavior at sub-zero
4 temperatures, particularly in direct comparison with LIBs, remains largely
5 unexplored, leaving uncertainty over the prospective applicability of this
6 technology in cold environments.

7 Consequently, in this work, two 18650 cylindrical SIB cells, a high-
8 energy and a high-power variant with layered metal oxide-based cathodes,
9 are systematically evaluated and compared with three LIB cells of the same
10 format utilizing different chemistries. Constant current discharge tests are
11 conducted to investigate their performance in terms of available capacity,
12 energy, and temperature rise in order to assess their application potential at
13 low and sub-zero temperatures.

14

15 **Results and Discussion**

16 The performance of the cells is described in terms of their provided capacity,
17 energy, average power, and experienced temperature increase within the CC
18 discharge at the target conditions. These results are visualized in Fig. 1. For
19 each case, two cell samples were tested. The bar represents the average value
20 of the two cells, while the error bar indicates the range between the individual
21 measurements.

1 **Fig. 1** The measurement results summarizing achieved capacity, energy,
 2 average power, and temperature increase across all the CC discharge tests.

3
 4 The overall capacity and energy levels at 25 °C for each chemistry
 5 correspond to the values listed in Table 1. Among them, LIB NMC exhibits
 6 the highest energy density, significantly surpassing the other chemistries in
 7 terms of capacity, energy, and power. Since its rated capacity is roughly
 8 twice that of the others, the absolute discharge currents at the corresponding
 9 C-rates are also higher. As a result, the cells achieve very high power mainly
 10 through high discharge currents, with higher voltage levels playing a smaller
 11 role. These high currents, however, also drive the strong heat generation and
 12 temperature rise. At 25 °C, this became performance-limiting: the cell

1 surface temperature reached 60 °C, triggering the safety cutoff by
2 temperature before the voltage limit was reached.

3 A strong temperature rise was also observed at low ambient
4 temperatures, which effectively improved performance by warming the cells
5 internally. For example, at -20 °C, the cells warmed up to -8.6 °C and 5 °C
6 during 0.3 C and 1 C discharges, respectively. In terms of low-temperature
7 operation, LIB NMC maintained proper functionality at 0.3 C and 1 C
8 discharges at -20 °C. However, at higher C-rates and/or lower ambient
9 temperatures, the cells became inoperable.

10 At the opposite end of the spectrum for capacity, energy, and power
11 is LIB LTO, which exhibits the lowest values. The first performance
12 limitation was observed in one cell during a 3 C discharge at -20 °C. At -30
13 °C, only about half of the nominal capacity could be achieved at 0.3 C, and
14 at lower temperatures or higher rates, the cells could not be discharged.

15 LIB LFP is positioned between NMC and LTO in terms of
16 performance, and at warmer temperatures it outperforms the SIB cells. The
17 decline of capacity and energy with decreasing temperature is more
18 pronounced than in other LIB chemistries. The two tested cells exhibited
19 heterogeneous behavior: one cell failed to discharge already at -10 °C and
20 -20 °C at the highest C-rates (2.4 C and 3 C), while the other operated
21 without limitations. This discrepancy can most likely be attributed to

1 manufacturing-related cell-to-cell variations. Small differences in
2 composition and structure have little effect under nominal conditions, but at
3 extreme conditions, such as very low temperatures combined with high
4 currents, they become significantly more pronounced, leading to reliability
5 issues. At $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, one cell could still be partially discharged at 0.3 C, but
6 beyond this point, neither cell was able to discharge further at such low
7 temperatures.

8 For SIBs, the HE cells deliver higher capacity and energy, as expected,
9 due to their larger capacity than SIB HP cells and consequently higher
10 absolute current values, as well as higher average power at warmer
11 temperatures. The first performance limitation for SIB HE was observed at
12 $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a 3 C discharge. At approximately ten degrees lower, only a 0.3
13 C discharge was possible, beyond which the cells could no longer be
14 discharged.

15 In contrast, SIB HP cells demonstrated stable discharge performance
16 across the entire current range down to $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. At $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, however, the
17 discharge capability was limited to about half of the nominal value, and one
18 cell showed reliability issues at 1.7 C. At this temperature, higher C-rates
19 were not feasible for either cell.

20 To compare the batteries in terms of energy at the lowest applied
21 current in this study, i.e., 0.3 C, representing often the nominal rate at electric

1 vehicle applications, Fig. 2 is provided. The figure highlights the clear
2 superiority of NMC LIB over all other investigated chemistries. Among the
3 remaining cells, LFP delivers the highest energy down to its operational
4 temperature limit of $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Beyond this point, one of the LFP cells exhibits
5 reliability issues and is surpassed by the SIBs, with SIB HP taking the lead.
6 Notably, SIB HP is the only chemistry that continues to function down to
7 $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

8
9 **Fig. 2** The energy available with 0.3 C discharge for the tested cells.

10

11 The characterization and performance comparison show that the
12 discharge capability of SIBs differs significantly at the lowest temperatures,
13 despite their identical electrode chemistry. This indicates that structural
14 design and other factors, defining the cells as HE or HP, play a crucial role.
15 The detailed 0.3 C discharge profiles for SIB HE are presented in Fig. 3,
16 where stronger temperature dependence and a larger voltage drop, caused by

1 higher resistance, can be observed compared to SIB HP under similar
 2 conditions (Fig. 4).

4 **Fig. 3** The 0.3 C discharge voltage profiles for SIB HE.

6 **Fig. 4** The 0.3 C discharge voltage profiles for SIB HP.

7

8 Selected performance indicators are summarized in Fig. 5. Overall, in
 9 terms of capacity, energy, and power, LIBs, particularly NMC and LFP,
 10 showed better discharge performance down to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Under restricted
 11 conditions and at low currents, LFP and LTO remained operable even at -30
 12 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, with SIB HE performing similarly, though slightly better. In contrast,
 13 SIB HP proved to be a strong candidate for low-temperature operation,
 14 maintaining full functionality down to $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and operating reasonably well,

1 though with some limitations, even at $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Temperature rise is typically
 2 viewed as undesirable because it reflects resistive losses and increases the
 3 burden on the thermal management system. However, at low ambient
 4 temperatures the associated self-heating can be advantageous, partially
 5 offsetting kinetic limitations by warming the cell toward more favorable
 6 operating conditions.

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8

9 **Fig. 5** Spider plot comparing six selected performance metrics of the tested
 10 cells. The lowest operational temperature is defined as the coldest ambient
 11 at which the cell delivers $\geq 50\%$ of its $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ energy at 1 C.

12

13 This study shows that some SIB cells, especially power-oriented
 14 designs, deliver better low-temperature discharge performance than the
 15 tested LIBs, and they work over a wider range of cold conditions. In practice,
 16 that can either give better performance with the same system design or
 17 reduce the need for battery heating (less preheating, smaller heaters), which

1 lowers cost and complexity and improves cold-start reliability. Likely use
2 cases, utilizing the characteristic low-temperature behavior of SIBs, include
3 applications in cold climate regions, such as outdoor consumer devices,
4 remote sensors and telemetry, telecommunications, light electric vehicles,
5 stationary energy storage systems, and also some specific aerospace
6 applications.

7

8 **Conclusion**

9 This work compared the low-temperature discharge behavior of five 18650
10 cells, two SIBs (HE, HP) and three LIBs (NMC, LFP, LTO), under constant-
11 current tests. At 25 °C, the NMC LIB delivered the highest energy and power
12 but was limited by heat generation at high current and lost operability below
13 about –30 °C. LFP and LTO remained only partially usable at –30 °C and
14 then only at low current, which was also the case for SIB HE. By contrast,
15 SIB HP maintained functionality down to –40 °C, albeit with reduced output.
16 These results indicate that suitably designed SIBs can be a promising
17 alternative for operation in extreme cold environments.

18 From an application perspective, SIBs can reduce preheating needs
19 and simplify thermal management for systems that must start and run in cold
20 climates, provided their lower energy density around 0 °C and above is
21 acceptable. Technology selection should therefore be made at the system

1 level, weighing cell performance together with thermal, electrical, and cost
2 constraints.

3 Future work should quantify power capability and impedance as a
4 function of state of charge to assess cold-start behavior more rigorously.
5 Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, in particular, can clarify mass-
6 transport and charge-transfer limitations. Mapping impedance together with
7 self-heating will inform thermal-management design and help quantify
8 potential advantages over LIBs. In addition, charging behavior and its limits
9 at low temperature warrant dedicated study, since charging is typically
10 permitted only at temperatures roughly 20–30 °C higher than those
11 acceptable for discharge.

12

13 **Experimental**

14 For this study, five types of 18650 cylindrical battery cells were used, and
15 the summary of their parameters is presented in Table 1. Among the tested
16 cells, there are two SIB cells, one designed as high energy (HE), and the
17 other as high power (HP). Additionally, three LIB cell types utilizing
18 chemistries based on nickel manganese cobalt (NMC), LFP, and lithium
19 titanate oxide (LTO) were used. The data in Table 1 were derived from
20 corresponding datasheets, except electrode material information, which was
21 determined by cell disassembly and measurement on the electrodes via

- 1 TESCAN VEGA 3 LMU, a scanning electron microscope (SEM) with
 2 energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS).
 3 **Table 1** Overview of the investigated battery cells.

Cell Type:	SIB HE	SIB HP	LIB NMC	LIB LFP	LIB LTO
Manufacturer	Hakadi	Hakadi	LG	JGN E	Huahui Energy
Nominal Capacity [Ah]	1.5	1.3	3.5	1.8	1.3
Nominal Voltage [V]	3.1	3.0	3.6	3.2	2.4
Volume Energy Density [Wh/l]	281	236	762	348	189
Gravimetric Energy Density [Wh/kg]	126	98	257	139	81
Cathode Material	$\text{Na}_x\text{Ni}_{1/3}\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{O}_2$	$\text{Na}_x\text{Ni}_{1/3}\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{O}_2$	$\text{LiNi}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$	LiFePO_4	$\text{LiCo}_{0.85}\text{Mn}_{0.15}\text{O}_2$
Anode Material	HC	HC	Gr-Si	Gr	$\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$

- 4
 5 A battery tester Neware BTS4000-5V12A was used for battery testing
 6 and measurement, while the cells were placed during the experiment in the
 7 thermally controlled environment in chambers Weiss WT3 600/70 and

1 Memmert ICP260+. For each test, two cells of the same type were used to
2 ensure repeatability and highlight heterogeneity or reliability issues linked
3 to the performance.

4 At first, a preconditioning test was applied to each of the cells, which
5 consisted of five nominal cycles, in order to stabilize the electrochemical
6 performance of the cells. Subsequently, the capacity tests were performed
7 with defined currents and at defined temperatures. The specific procedure of
8 the capacity tests consisted of ‘calibrated’ charging at 25 °C in constant
9 current – constant voltage (CCCV) mode, where the constant current of
10 0.5 C was used to achieve the respective voltage limits, and the charging
11 continued at the constant voltage until the current dropped below C/30.
12 Afterward, the cells were brought to and stabilized at the target temperature
13 (25, 0, –10, –20, –30, and –40 °C) to be discharged with the target constant
14 current (CC) (0.3, 1, 1.7, 2.4, 3 C). The LIB NMC maximum current was
15 limited only to 2.85 C, i.e., 10 A, to not exceed the datasheet’s limits.

16

17

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3

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13 *Figure Captions*

14 **Fig. 1** The measurement results summarizing achieved capacity, energy,
15 average power, and temperature increase across all the CC discharge tests.

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17 **Fig. 3** The 0.3 C discharge voltage profiles for SIB HE.

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1

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Anode Material	HC	HC	Gr-Si	Gr	$\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$

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1 *Figure 1*

2 *Figure 2*

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4 *Figure 3*

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1 *Figure 4*

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3 *Figure 5*

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5 **Graphical abstract**

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